

The temperature increase

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Now we calculate the temperature increase in the neighborhood of the radiation source. We assume that the whole room is a vacuum.

In Weigert [3] chapter 2.4.1. p.39 there is a calculation of surface temperatures of a planet without interior energy. With consideration of this we recognize, if E_e is the irradiance:

$$E_e \cdot (1 - A) \approx \sigma T_p^4 \quad (1)$$

$\sigma = 5,67 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{Watt m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-4}$ (constant of radiation)

$A =$ albedo $A \in [0, 1]$

$T_p =$ temperature of the planet's surface in Kelvin

In Voigt [2] II.9.2.3) p.71 there is the same temperature formula with an emission factor. This situation in vacuum means $A = 0$. It is obvious in our problem to follow:

$$E_e \approx \sigma(\Delta T)^4 \quad E_e = |\vec{E}_e| \quad (2)$$

$\Delta T =$ temperature increase by radiation

E_e can be determined generally with chapter 7 or chapter 12 in [1] and in special cases with chapter 11 at [1]. Then we can calculate the temperature increase.

If T_0 is the temperature in the room without the light source, $T = T_0 + \Delta T$ is the temperature in the room with light source.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001
- [2] Hans Heinrich Voigt "Abriß der Astronomie" 4.edition BI Mannheim 1988
- [3] Alfred Weigert, Heinrich J. Wendker "Astronomie und Astrophysik - ein Grundkurs" 2.edition VCH Weinheim 1989